

A New Synthetic Route to Thioammelides, related Thioethers and Ammelines. Part III : Interaction of Carbonyl Sulphide with S-Benzylamidinoisothiocarbamides

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Interaction of S-benzyl amidinoisothiocarbamides with carbonyl sulphide and appropriate follow-up treatment have been shown to result in the related thioammelides, thioethers and ammelines. Structures of some of the thioammelides so obtained have been established by their independent synthesis while structures of other products have been confirmed on the basis of their chemical reactions and ir spectra.

INTERACTION of carbon disulphide and S-benzyl amidino isothiocarbamides has been shown^{1,2,3} to afford thiadiazines and dithioammelides of the type III and IV. The latter on reaction with alkyl halides and amines formed the related thioethers (V) and thioammelines (VI) respectively. These reactions can be represented as follows :

Where R, R', R' and Ar are different substituent groups.

It has now been found that if carbonyl sulphide is used in place of carbon disulphide the reaction can be extended to the synthesis of corresponding oxygen analogues (VIII and IX). These, as expected, on reaction with an alkyl halide and amine form the related thioethers (X) and ammelines (XI) respectively. These changes can be stated as follows :

- Where in (a) R = R' = H & Bz = H
 (b) R = R' = Methyl & Bz = benzyl
 (c) R = *p*-tolyl ; R' = H & Bz = benzyl
 (d) R = R' = *p*-tolyl & Bz = benzyl
 R'' = ethyl or benzyl

The structures IXa and IXb have been confirmed by their independent synthesis by the acid hydrolysis of thioethers V (a), (b) prepared earlier^{1,3}.

Where (a) R = R' = H
 (b) R = R' = methyl

Experimental

Carbonyl sulphide was prepared following the procedure of Ganapathi and Venkataraman⁴. The gas was purified free from carbon dioxide by passing it through 33% caustic soda solution and then dried by passing it through conc. sulphuric acid.

Interaction of carbonyl sulphide with parent amidino-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (Ia) : Formation of 2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1, 3, 5-triazine (IXa) :

The required S-benzyl amidino isothiocarbamide was prepared as follows starting from amidinothiocarbamide obtained by Kurzer's⁵ procedure.

An ethanolic solution of amidinothiocarbamide and benzyl chloride was heated under reflux for 1.5 hr. when the hydrochloride of the expected S-benzyl amidino isothiocarbamide separated out ; on crystallisation from ethanol, m.p. 190°. Found : N, 22.4 ; S, 13.4 ; C₉H₁₂N₄S₂ requires N, 22.9 ; S, 13.1%.

An ethanolic solution of the related free base was obtained by suspending the hydrochloride (10 g) in absolute ethanol and neutralizing the acid with potassium hydroxide and filtering out the precipitated potassium chloride. A continuous, slow, stream of carbonyl sulphide was passed through the above ethanolic solution of Ia when the solution turned yellow and after about two hours a colourless solid (3 g) separated. On crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m. p. 350°. The compound is amphoteric in nature and could not be desulphurised with alkaline lead acetate. On analysis found : C, 24.96 ; H, 3.2 ; N, 39.3 ; S, 22.1 ; $C_3N_4H_4SO$ requires : C, 25.0 ; H, 2.8 ; N, 38.9 ; S, 22.2%. It was identified as 2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IXa). The structure IXa assigned to this product has been confirmed by the following synthesis.

Preparation of 2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IXa) by the hydrolysis of 2-thio-4-imino-6-mercaptoethyltetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (Va) :

A mixture of Va (0.5 g) and 5N hydrochloric acid (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hours when liberation of ethyl mercaptan was noticed. On filtration and cooling, a colourless solid separated, m. p. 350°; crystals from aq. ethanol, m. p. 350°. On analysis, found : S, 21.8 ; N, 38.4 ; $C_3H_4N_4SO$ requires : S, 22.2 ; N, 38.9%. Its ir spectrum was found superimposable on that of the product obtained in the preceding experiment.

Interaction of carbonyl sulphide with 1-methylamidino-3-methyl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (Ib) : Formation of 1-methyl-2-thio-4-methylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXb) :

1-methylamidino-3-methyl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide hydrochloride was prepared as described earlier⁶. A solution of the related free base (Ib) in toluene was then prepared by suspending the hydrochloride (2 g) in water, treating it with the calculated quantity of sodium hydroxide and extracting the free base with toluene. It was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

When carbonyl sulphide was passed through the above solution, within a few minutes a colourless solid separated and was filtered out (0.8 g). On crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 306°. On analysis found : C, 35.3 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 32.3 ; S, 18.2 ; $C_5H_8N_4SO$ requires : C, 34.9 ; H, 4.7 ; N, 32.6 ; S, 18.6%. It was identified as 1-methyl-2-thio-4-methylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXb) on the basis of its ir spectrum and the following synthesis. Its ir spectrum amongst others showed the following bands (cm^{-1}) : 3200m, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1670 w, C=O stretching in triazine (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675) ; 1620 s, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{8b}, 1685-1582) ; 1530 m, 1,3,5-triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500) ; 1200 m, 1190 m, N-C(=S)-N grouping (Lit.^{8d}, 1200-1100) ; 770 s, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750).

Synthesis of 1-methyl-2-thio-4-methylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXb) by the hydrolysis of 1-methyl-2-thio-4-methylimino-6-mercaptobenzyl-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (Vb) :

A mixture of 1-methyl-2-thio-4-methylimino-6-mercaptobenzyl-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine¹ (Vb, 0.5g) and 5N hydrochloric acid (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 4 hr. On filtration and cooling, a colourless crystalline solid separated, m.p. 306°. On recrystallisation from aq. ethanol, m. p. 305°. On analysis, found : S, 18.3 ; N, 32.1 ; $C_5H_8N_4SO$ requires : S, 18.6 ; N, 32.6%. It did not depress the m.p. of the product obtained in preceding experiment and its ir spectrum mapped on a Perkin Elmer, model 257, infrared spectrophotometer in KBr disc was also found superimposable on that of IXb described above.

Interaction of carbonyl sulphide with 1-p-tolyl-3-amidino-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (Ic) : Formation of 1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXc) :

1-p-Tolyl-3-amidino-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (Ic) was prepared by the benzylation of 1-p-tolyl-3-amidino thiocarbamide obtained by Kurzer's¹⁰ procedure. A continuous stream of carbonyl sulphide was passed through its well dried solution in toluene (5 g in 60 ml) when the solution turned yellow and after about 2hr. a colourless solid (2 g) separated. On filtration and washing with acetone, m.p. 340°. It was found insoluble in water and very sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetone. It did not desulphurise when warmed with alkaline plumbite solution. It was purified by reprecipitating it with dil. hydrochloric acid from its solution in ethanolic potassium hydroxide and finally crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. >340°. On analysis, found : C, 50.7 ; H, 3.8 ; N, 22.6 ; S, 13.5 ; $C_{10}H_{10}N_2OS$ requires : C, 51.2 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 23.0 ; S, 13.7%. On the basis of its chemical reactions and its ir spectrum it was identified as 1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXc). Its ir spectrum showed the following main bands (cm^{-1}) : 3200 s, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1700 s, C=O stretching in triazines (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675) ; 1650 m, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{8b}, 1685-1582) ; 1530 s, triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500) ; 1230 vs, C=S (Lit.¹¹, 1400-1100) ; 1150 s, N-C(=S)-N grouping (Lit.^{8d}, 1200-1100) ; 770 m, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750). These are in agreement with the structure assigned to it.

Interaction of carbonyl sulphide with 1-p-tolyl-3-p-tolylamidino-S-benzyl isothiocarbamide (Id) : Formation of 1-p-tolyl-2-thio-4-p-tolylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXd) :

The Id was prepared by benzylation of 1-p-tolyl-3-p-tolylamidino-thiocarbamide as described earlier⁸. On passing carbonyl sulphide in its solution in dry toluene (5 g in 100 ml) for about 3 hrs, a colourless solid separated and was filtered out (1.5 g). The product was purified by washing it freely with acetone. On analysis, found : C, 63.1 ; H, 5.1 ; N, 16.7 ; S, 10.0 ; $C_{17}H_{16}N_4SO$ requires : C, 63.0 ; H, 4.9 ; N, 17.3 ; S, 9.9%. This was probably the thiadiazine (VIIId). It was dissolved in ethanolic potash (1.4 g in 25 ml ethanolic potash (1.4 g in 25 ml ethanol) and the

resulting pale yellow solution warmed on water bath for 20 min and filtered. The clear, colourless filtrate on acidification with dil. hydrochloric acid afforded a colourless solid, m.p. 260°. On crystallisation from acetic acid, m.p. 272°. On analysis, found : C, 63.4 ; H, 5.2 ; N, 17.1 ; S, 10.1. $C_{17}H_{16}N_4SO$ requires : C, 63.0 ; H, 4.9 ; N, 17.3 ; S, 9.9%. It was identified as 1-*p*-tolyl-2-thio-4-*p* tolylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXd) on the basis of its chemical reaction (*vide infra*) and its ir spectrum. The more prominent bands (cm^{-1}) are assigned as follow : 3200 m, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1675 s, C=O stretching in triazines (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675) ; 1610 w, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{8b}, 1685-1582) ; 1570 w, 1520 s, triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500) ; 1220 vs, C=S, (Lit.¹¹, 1400-1100) ; 770 s, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750).

Interaction of benzyl chloride with thioammelides (IXa to IX d) : Formation of thioethers (Xa to Xd) :

Details of a typical experiment are as follows : A mixture of 2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IXa, 0.6 g), sodium hydroxide (0.2 g), benzyl chloride (1 ml) and ethanol (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 45 min. and on cooling filtered. The clear filtrate on evaporation left behind a colourless solid. On washing with petroleum ether and crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 215°. On analysis, found : C, 51.7 ; H, 4.6 ; N, 23.5 ; S, 13.3 ; $C_{10}H_{10}N_4SO$ requires : C, 51.3 ; H, 4.8 ; N, 23.9 ; S, 13.7%. It was identified as 2-mercaptobenzyl-4-imino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (Xa) on the basis of its ir spectrum which showed the following main bands (cm^{-1}) : 3300 m, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1700 m, C=O stretching in triazines (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675) ; 1630 s, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{8b}, 1685-1582) ; 1540 m, triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500).

1-Methyl - 2-thio-4 - methylimino- 6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXb) on benzylation with benzyl chloride under similar conditions afforded a product, m.p. 225° ; on crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 228°. On analysis, found : C, 55.2 ; H, 5.8 ; N, 21.2 ; S, 11.9 ; $C_{12}H_{14}N_4SO$ requires : C, 55.6 ; H, 5.7 ; N, 21.3 ; S, 12.2%. It was identified as 1-methyl-2-mercaptobenzyl-4-methylimino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1, 3, 5-(iso) triazine (Xb). Its ir spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}) : 3300 s, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1660 m, C=O stretch in triazines (Lit.^{8a}, 1775 1675) ; 1520 m, 1,3,5 triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500) ; 1410 m, CH₂ - S deformation (Lit.^{8a}, 1435-1410) ; 780 w, "is" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750).

1-*p*-Tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXc) on ethylation with ethyl bromide under conditions described above, afforded a colourless shining crystalline product ; on recrystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 195°. On analysis, found : C, 53.3 ; H, 5.7 ; N, 21.2 ; S, 12.0 ; $C_{12}H_{14}N_4SO$ requires : C, 54.9 ; H, 5.3 ; N, 21.4 ; S, 12.2%. It was identified

as 1-*p*-tolyl-2-mercaptoethyl-4-imino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (Xc where R''=ethyl). Its ir spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}) : 3100 m, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1675 s, C=O stretching in triazine (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675) ; 1565 m, triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500) ; 1230 s, CH₂S was (Lit.^{8a}, 1270-1220) ; 790 m, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750) ; which is in agreement with the structure Xc.

1-*p*-Tolyl-2-thio-4-*p*-tolylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXd) on analogous reaction with benzyl chloride afforded a colourless solid which was crystallised from aq. ethanol, m.p. 268°. On analysis, found : C, 69.0 ; H, 5.4 ; N, 13.5 ; S, 7.3 ; $C_{24}H_{22}N_4SO$ requires : C, 69.6 ; H, 5.3 ; N, 13.5 ; S, 7.7%. It was identified as 1-*p* tolyl-2-mercaptobenzyl-4-*p*-tolylimino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (Xd), on the basis of its ir spectrum which showed the following main bands (cm^{-1}) : 3200 w, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1700 s, C=O stretching in triazines (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675) ; 1600 s, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{8b}, 1685-1582) ; 1570 s, triazine ring (Lit.^{8c,9}, 1600-1500) ; 1420 m, CH₂ - S deformation (Lit.^{8a}, 1435-1410) ; 775 s, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750).

Interaction of benzyl amine with thioammelides (IXa to IXd) : Formation of ammelines (XIa to XI d) :

Details of a typical experiment are as follows : A mixture of 2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-triazine (IXa, 0.8 g) and benzyl amine (2 ml) was heated on an oil bath at 180° for 30 min when liberation of H₂S was noticed. On cooling and washing with dil. hydrochloric acid, a solid (0.5 g) remained behind. On crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 170°. On analysis, found : C, 54.9 ; H, 4.5 ; N, 31.8 ; $C_{10}H_{11}N_5O$ requires : C, 55.3 ; H, 5.0 ; N, 31.9%. It was identified as 2-benzylamino-4-imino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-triazine (XIa). The same product is obtained by the reaction of benzylamine with Xa.

1-M e t h y l-2-thio-4-methylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXb) on reaction with benzyl amine under analogous conditions afforded a solid, m.p. 170°. On crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 172°. On analysis, found : N, 28.3 ; $C_{12}H_{15}N_5O$ requires : N, 28.6%. It was identified as 1-methyl-2-benzylamino-4-methylimino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (XIb). The same product was obtained by the reaction of benzyl amine with (Xb). Its ir spectrum showed the following bands (cm^{-1}) : 3300 s, NH stretching, (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100) ; 1620 s, C=O stretching (Lit.^{8a}, 1695-1630) ; 1570 m, triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 1600-1500) ; 740 s, "is" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750).

1-*p*-Tolyl-2-thio-4-imino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine IXc on reaction with benzyl amine afforded a solid, m.p. 234° ; on crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 234°. On analysis, found : N, 22.4 ; $C_{17}H_{17}N_5O$ requires : N, 22.8%. On the basis of its ir spectrum it was identified as 1-*p*-tolyl-2-benzylamino-4 imino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (XIc). Following assignments have been made for the main bands (cm^{-1}) :

3220 w, NH stretching (Lit.⁷, 3400-3100); 1680 s C=O stretching in triazine (Lit.^{8a}, 1775-1675); 1620 m, N-C=N grouping (Lit.^{8b}, 1685-1582); 1560 s, triazine ring (Lit.^{8c}, 1600-1500); 790 m, "iso" form of triazine ring (Lit.^{8a}, 795-750). Reaction of benzyl amine and Xc afforded the same product, XIc, m.p. & m.m.p. 234°.

1-*p*-Tolyl-2-thio-4-*p*-tolylimino-6-oxo-hexahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (IXd) on similar reaction with benzyl amine afforded a solid, m.p. 210°. On crystallisation from aq. ethanol, m.p. 210°. On analysis, found: C, 72.8; H, 6.1; N, 17.3; C₂₄H₂₃N₅O requires: C, 72.5; H, 5.8; N, 17.6%. It was identified as 1-*p*-tolyl-2-benzylamino-4-*p*-tolylimino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (XIId).

Reaction of benzyl amine and 1-*p*-tolyl-2-mercaptobenzyl-4-*p*-tolylimino-6-oxo-tetrahydro-1,3,5-(iso) triazine (Xd) also afforded the same product (XIId); m.p. and m.m.p. 210°.

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